

Light-scattering Studies on Gum Catechu in Aqueous and Hydrochloric Acid Solutions

J. N. Chakravarti and S. N. Mukherjee

The molecular weight of the catechuic acid has been observed to be 4.8×10^6 after taking into account all necessary corrections. The molecular length is about 227 μ in aqueous solution, varying to 196 μ in 0.06*N*-HCl. The gradual decrease in length of the molecule in higher concentrations of HCl has been ascribed to the suppression of the acidic dissociation in presence of similarly charged ions.

Considerable work was carried out on gum arabic¹⁻³ which is regarded as a random-coil type polysaccharide of ionic nature. The arabic acid²⁻³ was found to undergo a rapid contraction in length in presence of common ions. A similar behaviour was also noted by Katchalsky and Eisenberg⁴ when polyvinyl phosphate, a linear colloidal electrolyte, was dipped into acid. A nonionic polysaccharide, viz., guar gum³, on the other hand, exhibits no such change on addition of extraneous ions.

In view of these interesting behaviours of polysaccharides, which received comparatively little attention, it was considered useful to investigate the behaviour of one of such typical polysaccharides, the catechuic acid, derived from gum catechu. In our previous communication⁵, we examined its behaviour in aqueous and 0.02*N*-HCl solutions. The present communication records detailed light-scattering studies on the same when it is treated with hydrochloric acid of different strengths.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method of preparation of the sample has been previously mentioned⁷. A weighed quantity of the substance was taken and dissolved in water by shaking. The solution was allowed to settle for about 24 hr. Both water and the catechuic acid solutions were made dust-free by repeated filtration through sintered glass funnels (No. 4). Scattering measurements were made in a Brice-Phoenix Light Scattering Photometer (Phoenix Precision Instrument Company), using a semi-octagonal dissymmetry cell. The wave length of the unpolarised light used was 436 μ .

The turbidity of the solution was calculated from the record of the scattering ratio of the light intensity at -90° and at 0° . Turbidity of the solvent was also similarly

1. Halwar *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 73, 2786.
2. Veiss and Eggenberger, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 1560.
3. Mukherjee and Deb, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 823.
4. *Nature*, 1950, 166, 287.
5. Deb and Mukherjee, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 413.
6. Chakravarti and Mukherjee, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 811.
7. Kulshrestha *et al.*, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1962, 54, 206.

determined and it was subtracted from that of the solution. Thus the absolute turbidity (T) was determined. The turbidities of a number of solutions of progressively lower concentrations were ascertained by subtraction of the turbidity of the solvent in each case.

The dissymmetry (Z) measurements for different concentrations were made in the usual way. The fluorescence of the solution was tested by imposing a yellow filter on the nose of the photomultiplier. A small deflection was observed and no correction for this effect was found necessary. Depolarisation (ρ_u) effect was calculated by the usual procedure. The depolarisation correction factor (Cabbane's factor)

$$\left(\frac{6+6\rho_u}{6-7\rho_u} \right) c \rightarrow 0$$

was evaluated by extrapolation.

The specific refractive increments were determined by means of a Brice-Phoenix Differential Refractometer (Phoenix Precision Instrument Company), maintaining a temperature of 28°. The entire process, described above, was repeated at steps when the catechuic acid was dissolved respectively in water and 0.001*N*, 0.006*N*, 0.02*N*, 0.04*N*, and 0.08*N*-HCl.

DISCUSSION

The values of Hc/T for a series of concentrations were calculated and plotted against concentration (c). The reciprocal of the intercept was taken after extrapolating to zero concentration and hence the molecular weight, uncorrected for any interference effect, was determined, using the relation:

$$(Hc/T) \cdot P_{90} = 1/M + 2Bc \cdot P_{90} \quad \dots (1)$$

where

$$H = 32 \pi^3 \cdot n_0^2 [(n-n_0/c)^2/2N\lambda^4] \quad \dots (2)$$

c is the concentration of the solute in g./ml; M is the weight average molecular weight of the solute; B is a constant; n is the refractive index of the solution and n_0 , that of the solvent; λ is the wave length of the incident light in cm; N , the Avogadro number, and T , the absolute turbidity of the solution; $(n-n_0)$ is the refractive increment of the solution and P_{90} , the particle-scattering factor at 90°.

It appears from Fig. 1 that at low concentrations of the catechuic acid in aqueous medium, the plot exhibits a high slope. As the concentration is gradually increased, the slope decreases and finally the curve becomes almost parallel to the c -axis. On account of this curvature in the lower concentration range, the extrapolation to zero concentration becomes uncertain. The difficulty could not be avoided even by using 0.001*N*-HCl or 0.006*N*-HCl as the solvent medium. When the strength was further increased to 0.02*N*, the curve became linear, thus rendering easy and accurate extrapolation. From the value of Hc/T , when extrapolated to zero concentration, the molecular weight was calculated. The value from the intercept comes out to be 1.3×10^6 which needs further correction for dissymmetry (Z) of scattering and also of depolarisation.

The dissymmetry values (Z) of catechuic acid in aqueous and in HCl solutions of different strengths were extrapolated to zero concentration (Fig. 2). Assuming the catechuic acid to be a polydisperse macromolecule of random-coil type⁶⁻⁷, the intrinsic dissymmetry in 0.02*N*-HCl was calculated for the correction factor. The molecular weight after this correction comes out to be 3.9×10^6 . Multiplying this value with Cabanne's factor (=1.15 in this case), the molecular weight becomes 4.5×10^6 .

FIG. 1. Variation of Hc/T with concentration.

FIG. 2. Variation of dissymmetry with concentration.

The molecular weight can also be calculated from the linear curves obtained in Fig. 1, when catechuic acid is dissolved in 0.04*N*- and 0.06*N*-HCl. The values come out to be 4.8×10^6 and 5.1×10^6 after making all the corrections. The mean value of the molecular weight from all these observations thus equals 4.8×10^6 .

The dimensions of the catechuic acid molecule in aqueous and in HCl medium can

FIG. 3. Variation of molecular length with the concentration of the solvent (HCl).

be calculated from the corresponding intrinsic dissymmetry values. It appears that the root-mean-square end-to-end distance of the gum molecule is 327 μ in aqueous solution which gradually decreases to 196 μ in 0.06*N*-HCl (Fig. 3).

Concentrations higher than 0.06 *N*-HCl could not be used as it was likely to affect the content of the optical cell used.

⁶The nature of the ($Z-c$) curve obtained with 0.06*N*-HCl was anomalous due to appearance of a slight turbidity and was therefore discarded.

7. Stacy, "Light Scattering in Physical Chemistry", Butterworth Scientific Publications, 1956.

It appears that the reduction in molecular length is due to the suppression of the acidic dissociation of catechuic acid in presence of excess of H^+ ions, although the molecular weight remains unchanged.

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for financing this scheme of research in the earlier stage.

RAMKRISHNA MISSION RESIDENTIAL COLLEGE,
NARENDRAPUR,
24 PARAGANAS, WEST BENGAL
and
PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY, CALCUTTA-32.

Received December 7, 1964.